

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROBABILISTIC AND CONTINUUM DESCRIPTIONS OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF BRITTLE-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY : Internal variables modeling the degradation mechanisms occurring in brittle-matrix composites are related to microscopic quantities by using a probabilistic approach to failure. Two examples are presented. The first one deals with matrix-cracking and the second one is concerned with debonding and slip. In both cases, it is shown that in general the moments of order higher than one are needed to describe the behavior in a Continuum Mechanics framework.

KEYWORDS: Continuum Thermodynamics, state potential, internal variables, matrix-cracking, debonding and slip, fiber breakage, failure probability.

INTRODUCTION

Constitutive laws of (composite) materials can be written within the framework of Continuum Thermodynamics [1]. The aim is to describe the degradation mechanisms occurring in brittle-matrix composites by internal variables introduced in a state potential. The state potential $\bar{\psi}$ is made up of two terms, viz. a recoverable part $\bar{\psi}^e$ and non-recoverable part $\bar{\psi}^i$. The recoverable part is usually referred to as elastic energy density and the non-recoverable part corresponds to elastic energy densities associated with residual stresses induced by the degradation mechanisms. The state potential is postulated very often. The scope of the present study is to show that the state potential can be evaluated and that the internal variables defined at a continuum level can be related to the distribution of microscopic quantities characterizing the degradation mechanisms.

The present study deals with matrix-cracking, interface debonding and slip as well as fiber breakage occurring in brittle matrices reinforced by continuous fibers. For the sake of simplicity, unidirectional architectures are discussed. At a microscopic level, the crack locations are randomly distributed within the material. At a mesoscopic level (i.e., Continuum Mechanics level) the behavior is described by internal variables. The relationship between the two descriptions is derived and the relevant variables are introduced to model the above-mentioned degradation mechanisms.

GENERAL FRAMEWORK

Upon loading, a fiber reinforced composite experiences multiple matrix-cracking accompanied by interfacial debonding and slip. The system studied herein (Fig. 1), contains matrix cracks randomly distributed and characterized by a probability density function $F(L)$ which evolves with the applied mesoscopic stress $\bar{\sigma}$.

Fig. 1: Elementary cells

The matrix cracks induce an increment of the Gibbs free enthalpy $\Delta\bar{\varphi}^e$

$$\Delta\bar{\varphi}^e = \frac{1}{\bar{L}} \int_0^{+\infty} \Delta\varphi^e(L) L F(L) dL \quad \text{with} \quad \bar{L} = \int_0^{+\infty} L F(L) dL \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\varphi^e(L)$ is the Gibbs energy density increment related to a crack in a cell of length L . This result assumes that the only considered interactions are those due to the closest neighboring cracks. The long distance interactions are therefore neglected. Debonding and sliding induce inelastic strains $\bar{\varepsilon}^i$ and hysteresis loops [2]. Application of the principle of virtual work yields

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^i = \frac{1}{\bar{L}} \int_0^{+\infty} \left[\int_0^L \frac{\sigma_f^r(z, L)}{E_f} dz \right] F(L) dL \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_f^r(z, L)$ is the residual stress field induced by sliding in the fiber, z the current position in a cell of length L . The corresponding stress field is self-balanced and enables to store energy $\bar{\psi}^i$

$$\bar{\psi}^i = \frac{E f E_f}{2(1-f) E_m \bar{L}} \int_0^{+\infty} \left[\int_0^L \left\{ \frac{\sigma_f^r(z, L)}{E_f} \right\}^2 dz \right] F(L) dL \quad (3)$$

where f is the fiber volume fraction, E_f , E_m and E are the respective Young's moduli of the fiber, the matrix and the undamaged composite ($E = fE_f + (1-f)E_m$).

The degradation mechanisms in the composite are described by internal variables. Matrix-cracking is modeled by a damage variable D defined by [3]

$$\Delta\bar{\varphi}^e = \bar{\varphi}^e(D) - \bar{\varphi}^e(D=0) = \frac{\bar{\sigma}^2}{2E(1-D)} \quad (4)$$

Equations (1) and (4) show that the damage variable D is a function of all the moments associated with the probability density function F . The inelastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}^i$ is one of the variables modeling interfacial degradation (i.e., debonding and sliding). The second variable, d , is obtained from the expression of the non-recoverable part of the free energy density $\bar{\psi}^i$

$$\bar{\psi}^i = \frac{E(\bar{\varepsilon}^i)^2}{2d} \quad (5)$$

This expression was also used in the study of cracking in concrete and rocks [4]. The Helmholtz free energy density $\bar{\psi}$ is given by

$$\bar{\psi} = \frac{E(1-D)}{2}(\bar{\varepsilon} - \bar{\varepsilon}^i)^2 + \frac{E(\bar{\varepsilon}^i)^2}{2d} \quad (6)$$

and the associated forces to the state variables are expressed as

$$\bar{\sigma} = \frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}}, \quad Y = -\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial D}, \quad y = -\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial d}, \quad \bar{X} = -\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}^i} \quad (7)$$

Equation (7.1) gives the definition of the mesoscopic stress, Eqn (7.2) introduces the energy release rate density, Eqn (7.3) specifies the energy release of residual stresses due to sliding and Eqn (7.4) characterizes the back-stress associated with friction. The evolution laws of the internal variables can be obtained either by using micromechanical analyses (see below) or by macroscopic experiments (Fig. 2). In particular, the calculation of the damage variable d needs the evaluation of the non-recoverable free energy density $\bar{\psi}^i$: see for instance Chrysochoos et al. [5] or Cho et al. [6].

Fig. 2: Mesoscopic stress/strain curve

By way of an example, two particular cases are now investigated.

APPLICATIONS

In this first example we only consider matrix-cracking. By using the Cox' model [7], the recoverable part of the free energy density $\Delta\phi^e(L)$ can be calculated

$$\Delta\phi^e(L) = \frac{(1-f)E_m}{fE_f} \frac{\tanh(\beta L)}{\beta L} \frac{\bar{\sigma}^2}{2E} \quad (8)$$

where β is a constant dependent upon the elastic and geometric properties of the matrix and the fiber (β is inversely proportional to the fiber radius R). A characteristic length L_r associated to matrix-cracking is defined by

$$\Delta\varphi^e(L_r) = \Delta\bar{\varphi}^e \quad (9)$$

To calculate $\Delta\bar{\varphi}^e$, the probability density function $F(L)$ is derived by assuming that the flaws are distributed according to a Poisson point process. Under this assumption, the distribution of fragments $F(L)$ can be written as (see for example Ref. 8)

$$F(L) = \lambda_t(\sigma) \exp[-\lambda_t(\sigma)] \quad (10)$$

where $\lambda_t(\sigma)$ denotes the density of broken flaws. When the density $\lambda_t(\sigma)$ is assumed to be modeled by a power-law function of the local stress σ , a Weibull model is retrieved. The average fragment length \bar{L} is related to $\lambda_t(\sigma)$ by

$$\bar{L} = \frac{1}{\lambda_t(\sigma)} \quad (11)$$

The average variation of the free enthalpy density becomes

$$\Delta\bar{\varphi}^e = \frac{(1-f)E_m}{fE_f} \frac{1}{\beta\bar{L}} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta\bar{L}} G\left(\frac{1}{2\beta\bar{L}}\right) - 1 \right] \frac{\bar{\sigma}^2}{2E} \quad (12)$$

where G is the Bateman function, Laplace transform of the hyperbolic tangent [9]. Equation (12) shows that the damage variable D (see Eqn (4)) and the normalized representative length βL_r (see Eqn (9)) are non-trivial functions of $\beta\bar{L}$

$$\frac{\tanh(\beta L_r)}{\beta L_r} = \frac{1}{\beta\bar{L}} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta\bar{L}} G\left(\frac{1}{2\beta\bar{L}}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (13)$$

In particular, this function is different from that obtained by assuming that $\Delta\varphi^e(\bar{L}) = \Delta\bar{\varphi}^e$ for which

$$L_r = \bar{L} \quad (14)$$

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the error $\Delta\bar{L}$ defined by

$$\Delta\bar{L} = |L_r - \bar{L}| \quad (15)$$

For large values of $\beta\bar{L}$, the two lengths are virtually identical. On the other hand when $\beta\bar{L}$ decreases, the two lengths separate from each other. Consequently, the length \bar{L} is not necessarily the characteristic quantity to describe the damage variable D .

In the following, we consider that the cracking and debonding/sliding mechanisms are uncoupled. Therefore the previous results are still valid even though debonding/sliding will be added. We also assume that the interface toughness is vanishingly small and that the interfacial behavior is approached by a constant interfacial shear resistance τ [10, 2]. The equivalent debond length l_{de} is defined through the expression of the inelastic strain

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^i = \frac{\tau l_{de}^2}{2E_f R L_r} \quad (16)$$

The inelastic strain depends upon the distribution of crack distances and debond lengths. The evaluation of the damage variable d is obtained from the non-recoverable part of the free

energy density (see Eqn (3)). When the minimum distance between two adjacent cracks is greater than the debond length, the latter takes a unique value and the damage variable d is written as

$$d = \frac{3(1-f)E_m l_{de}}{4fE_f L_r} \quad (17)$$

This result is only valid when the interfacial behavior verifies the hypotheses of this section. When the interfacial behavior is more complex, the variable d is proportional to the ratio l_{de} / L_r provided the stress field in front of the crack tip is that of the undamaged material.

Fig. 3: Relative error $\Delta L / L_r$ versus normalized average length βL

To illustrate the previous results, we will study a single filament in which the matrix is more resistant than the fiber. This is a classical test configuration to characterize the interfacial properties of the composite. The features of the macroscopic stress/strain curve are dominated by the debonding and sliding mechanisms since the average distance between matrix cracks (at saturation) is two or three orders of magnitude greater than the fiber radius ($\beta \bar{L} \approx 10^2, 10^3$). Therefore the value of the damage variable D is negligible and the representative length L_r is identical to the average crack distance \bar{L} . To determine the equivalent length l_{de} , one needs the evaluation of the inelastic strain $\bar{\epsilon}^i$ as a function of the applied stress $\bar{\sigma}$. In the case of a constant interfacial shear resistance τ , two alternate routes can be followed. The first one is analytical. For an isolated break, an exclusion zone in which no further break can occur can be exhibited. When a break is located at $z = 0$, no new break can be created in the interval $]-l_R / 2, +l_R / 2[$ since the stress level remains less than the failure stress at $z = 0$ (Fig. 4). The length l_R is expressed as [10]

$$l_R = \frac{RT}{\tau} \quad (18)$$

where T denotes the stress level in an unbroken fiber.

Fig. 4: Depiction of an exclusion zone

Gulino and Phoenix [11] propose an approximation of the fragmentation process by assuming that it remains a Poisson point process throughout the whole history. The drawback of this model is that it is unable to capture the saturation of cracking. To improve the result, one may use a Boolean random islands model [12, 13] which constitutes a *lower* bound to the number of broken flaws. This model does not account for exclusion overlappings and *over-estimates* the zone over which defects cannot break. The flaw density $\lambda_f(T)$ is described by a power-law function of the local stress T

$$\lambda_f(T) = \frac{1}{L_0} \left(\frac{T}{S_0} \right)^m \quad (19)$$

where m and $L_0 S_0^m$ are the Weibull parameters. Two characteristic parameters S_c and δ_c can be exhibited [14, 15] by using the relationship $\lambda_f(S_c) l_R(S_c) = 1$

$$S_c^{m+1} = \frac{L_0 S_0^m \tau}{R} \quad \text{and} \quad \delta_c = l_R(S_c) \quad (20)$$

Therefore, the density of broken defects λ_b per unit characteristic length δ_c verifies

$$\lambda_b(\bar{T}) \geq \frac{m}{m+1} \gamma \left[\frac{m}{m+1}, \bar{T}^{m+1} \right] \quad \text{with} \quad \bar{T} = \frac{T}{S_c} \quad (21)$$

where γ is the incomplete gamma function. This result possesses the interesting property of reasonably describing the saturation process (see Table 1). Besides, the expression for the probability density function $F(L)$ derived in the previous example will be used as a first approximation. To compute the average inelastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}^i$, Eqn (2) can be rewritten as

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^i = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^{\infty} L \varepsilon^i(L) F(L) dL \quad (22)$$

where $\varepsilon^i(L)$ denotes the inelastic strain of a cell of length L . For an interface with a constant shear resistance τ , the inelastic strain $\varepsilon^i(L)$ is expressed as

$$\varepsilon^i(L) = \begin{cases} \frac{f\tau}{(1-f)RE_m} \left(l_R - \frac{L}{2} \right) & \text{when } L < l_R \\ \frac{f\tau l_R^2}{2(1-f)LRE_m} & \text{when } L \geq l_R \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

so that the inelastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}^i$ becomes

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^i = \frac{f\tau l_R}{(1-f)RE_m} - \frac{f\tau \bar{L}}{(1-f)RE_m} \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{l_R}{\bar{L}}\right) \right] \quad (24)$$

By using Eqn (16) and replacing l_{de} by l_{Re} , fE_f by $(1-f)E_m$ (the role played by the matrix and the fiber are inverted in a monofilament test), one obtains

$$l_{Re}^2 = 2\bar{L}l_R - 2\bar{L}^2 \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{l_R}{\bar{L}}\right) \right] \quad (25)$$

A first order approximation about $l_R / \bar{L} = 0$ yields

$$l_{Re} \approx l_R \quad (26)$$

This result again shows that the representative length l_{Re} can be approximated by l_R as a first order evaluation but diverges for higher values of l_R / \bar{L} . The non-recoverable part of the free energy density $\bar{\psi}^i$ given by Eqn (3) can be rewritten as

$$\bar{\psi}^i = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^{\infty} L \psi^i(L) F(L) dL \quad (27)$$

where $\psi^i(L)$ denotes the non-recoverable free energy density of a cell of length L . When the interfacial shear strength is assumed to be constant, $\psi^i(L)$ is expressed as

$$\psi^i(L) = \begin{cases} \frac{fE\tau^2}{(1-f)E_mE_fR^2} \left(\frac{l_R^2}{2} - \frac{Ll_R}{2} + \frac{L^2}{6} \right) & \text{when } L < l_R \\ \frac{fE\tau^2}{(1-f)E_mE_fR^2} \frac{l_R^3}{6L} & \text{when } L \geq l_R \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

so that the average free energy density $\bar{\psi}^i$ becomes

$$\bar{\psi}^i = \frac{fE\tau^2}{(1-f)E_mE_fR^2} \left[\frac{l_R^2}{2} - \bar{L}l_R + \bar{L}^2 \left\{ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{l_R}{\bar{L}}\right) \right\} \right] \quad (29)$$

By using Eqn (3), the following expression for the damage parameter d is found

$$d = \frac{fE_f}{(1-f)E_m} \frac{\frac{1}{2} \left[l_R + \bar{L} \left\{ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{l_R}{\bar{L}}\right) \right\} \right]^2}{\frac{l_R^2}{2} - \bar{L}l_R + \bar{L}^2 \left\{ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{l_R}{\bar{L}}\right) \right\}} \quad (30)$$

A first order approximation of d about $l_R / \bar{L} = 0$ yields

$$d \approx \frac{3fE_f}{4(1-f)E_m} \frac{l_R}{\bar{L}} \quad (31)$$

This result is identical to that of Eqn (17) by inverting fE_f and $(1-f)E_m$ (the role of the matrix and the fiber is inverted in the fragmentation test of a monofilament).

To account for exclusion, a key issue close to saturation, one may use other approaches. Curtin [15] bases his approach on a hard core sphere model [16]. This model has been shown to be an approximation of the so-called ‘exact’ solution [17]. All these approaches are analytical. One can also use numerical solutions based upon a Monte-Carlo simulation. When the interfacial shear strength τ is assumed to be constant, a numerical solution is not necessarily needed, even though it has been used [14]. One may note that when the exclusion phenomena are not as simple as those alluded to, a numerical method is the only viable alternative [18-20].

To study the evolution of the representative length l_{Re} , we now use a numerical analysis for the sake of simplicity. To check the results, a comparison (Table 1) of the broken flaw density λ_b per unit length δ_c is performed with data obtained by Hui et al. [17], Curtin [15] and Henstenburg and Phoenix [14].

Table 1: Broken flaw density at saturation $\lambda_b(\infty)$ versus Weibull modulus m by using different methods

m	Henstenburg ¹	Curtin ²	Hui ³	Eqn (21)	Meth. 1	Meth. 2
3	1.03	1.03	1.05	0.92	1.06	1.05
5	1.13	1.15	1.13	0.94	1.14	1.14
10	1.24	1.24	1.24	0.96	1.25	1.24
15	1.29	1.30	1.29	0.98	1.30	1.30
∞	1.49*	1.49*	1.50	1.00	1.48*	1.49*

¹ = [14], ² = [15], ³ = [17], *: $m = 1000$.

Two routes can be followed. The first one (referred to as method No. 1), is very close to a finite element concept. It consists in discretizing a length L_{tot} elements of identical length dz and experiencing one failure at most. A Poisson point process is used such that the probability of finding a broken flaw within $dz \ll L_{tot}$ is $dz\lambda_t$. A random generator of ‘good’ quality [21] can create a sequence of random failure stresses according to the previous probability. The fragmentation history is defined by ranking the previous sequence in ascending order and by checking that a defect able to break is not located in an exclusion zone of a previously broken flaw. This procedure is carried out until all the failure stresses have been analyzed. It is very easy to program but is memory-consuming since all the failure stresses need to be stored. This model approaches the analytical solution obtained for an infinite length (see for instance Ref. 8). The limitation of the method is the number of elements (of the order of 10^5 in our case). The results of 10 realizations per Weibull moduli are shown in Table 1. The analyzed length is $L_{tot} = 10^3 \delta_c$ and the element length is $dz = 10^{-2} \delta_c$.

The second route (referred to as method No. 2) is less demanding on memory but may turn out to be more time-consuming than the previous one when the number of broken flaws increases. The only stresses to be stored are those of the broken flaws. The hypotheses are identical to method No. 1 ($L_{tot} = N_{tot} \times dz$). The difference comes from the computation of the stress step which is chosen in order to break one flaw, if it is not located in an exclusion zone of an already broken flaw. The stress step ΔT is such that: $dz \cdot \partial\lambda_t / \partial t(T) \Delta T = 1$; the defect position is randomly selected according to a uniform distribution over a length L_{tot} . The search for all the exclusion zones of the broken flaws can penalize this method since it has to be performed for each new defect. This model approaches the analytical solution obtained for an infinite length (see for instance Ref. 8). The results of 10 realizations per Weibull moduli are also shown in Table 1 for a length $L_{tot} = 10^3 \delta_c$ and an element length $dz = 10^{-3} \delta_c$. The results of Table 1 show that the two numerical methods lead to values very close to those found by Hui et al. [17]. To avoid end effects, periodicity conditions are enforced to choose exclusion zones.

Figure 5 shows the normalized equivalent length l_{Re} / \bar{L} as a function of the normalized recovery length l_R / \bar{L} for a Weibull modulus $m = 3$. The three approaches lead to the same result when $l_R / \bar{L} \ll 1$: $l_R \approx l_{Re}$. However, there are differences when l_R / \bar{L} increases. The results of a realization ($\lambda_b(\infty) = 1.051$) with method No. 2 (denoted by Num.), those of an approximation (denoted by Approx.) by a Poisson point process (Eqn (25)) and those for which the overlapping of exclusion zones is neglected ($l_{Re} \approx l_R$). The approximation by a Poisson point process *over-estimates* the number of failures and therefore *under-estimates* the inelastic strain $\bar{\epsilon}^i$ and the equivalent length l_{Re} . On the contrary, the equality $l_{Re} = l_R$

constitutes an upper bound since it does not account for exclusion overlappings: it *overestimates* the equivalent length l_{Re} .

Fig. 5: Normalized equivalent length l_{Re} / L versus normalized recovery length l_R / L . Three different approaches are used ($m = 3$)

CONCLUSIONS

All these results show that the choice for equivalent lengths to describe matrix-cracking, debonding/sliding equal to their average values is only valid as a first order approximation. The description of representative lengths in an elementary cell is therefore an important task in itself. If one wants to characterize degradation mechanisms by microscopic observations, average lengths certainly represent relevant quantities to measure. On the other hand, if the aim is to describe their influence on the mechanical behavior, other elements of the distribution length can be of importance (i.e., not only averages need to be considered). A full micromechanical analysis is needed to know the exact meaning of each length.

REFERENCES

1. Germain, P., Nguyen, Q.S. and Suquet, P., "Continuum Thermodynamics", *ASME J. Appl. Mech.*, Vol. 50, 1983, pp. 1010-1020.
2. Aveston, J., Cooper, G.A. and Kelly, A., "Single and Multiple Fracture", *National Physical Laboratory: Properties of Fiber Composites* (1971), pp. 15-26.
3. Lemaitre, J. and Dufailly, J., "Modélisation et identification de l'endommagement plastique des métaux", *3^e congrès français de mécanique* (1977).
4. Andrieux, S., Bamberger, Y. and Marigo, J.-J., "Un modèle de matériau microfissuré pour les bétons et les roches", *J. Méc. Th. Appl.*, Vol. 5, No. 3, 1986, pp. 471-513.
5. Chrysochoos, A., Maisonneuve, O., Martin, G. and Caumon, H., "Plastic and Dissipated Work and Stored Energy", *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, Vol. 114, 1987, pp. 323-333.
6. Cho, C. Holmes, J.W. and Barber, J.R., "Estimation of Interfacial Shear in Ceramic Composites from Frictional Heating Measurements", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 74, No. 11, 1991, pp. 2802-2808.
7. Cox, H.L., "The Elasticity and the Strength of Paper and other Fibrous Materials", *Br. J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 3, 1952, pp. 72-79.
8. Grady, D.E., "Particle Size Statistics in Dynamic Fragmentation", *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 68, No. 12, 1990, pp. 6099-6105.
9. Spanier, J. and Oldham, K.B., "An Atlas of Function", Springer, New York, NY (USA), 1987.

10. Kelly, A. and Tyson, W.R., "Tensile Properties of Fiber-Reinforced Metals: Copper/Tungsten and Copper/Molybdenum", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 13, 1965, pp. 329-350.
11. Gulino, R. and Phoenix, S.L., "Weibull Strength Statistics for Graphite Fibres Measured from the Break Progression in a Model Graphite/Glass/Epoxy Microcomposite", *J. Mater. Sci.*, Vol. 26, No. 11, 1991, pp. 3107-3118.
12. Jeulin, D., "Anisotropic Rough Surface Modeling by Random Morphological Functions", *Acta Stereol.*, Vol. 6, 1987, pp. 183-189.
13. Serra, J., "Boolean Random Functions", *Image Analysis and Mathematical Morphology, Volume 2: Theoretical Advances*, Academic Press, London (UK), 1988.
14. Henstenburg, R.B. and Phoenix, S.L., "Interfacial Shear Strength Studies Using the Single-Filament-Composite Test. Part II: A Probability Model and Monte Carlo Simulations", *Polym. Comp.*, Vol. 10, No. 5, 1989, pp. 389-406.
15. Curtin, W.A., "Exact Theory of Fiber Fragmentation in Single-Filament Composite", *J. Mater. Sci.*, Vol. 26, 1991, pp. 5239-5253.
16. Widom, B., "Random Sequential Addition of Hard Spheres to a Volume", *J. Chem. Phys.*, Vol. 44, No. 10, 1966, pp. 3888-3894.
17. Hui, C.Y., Phoenix, S.L., Ibnabdeljalil, M. and Smith, R.L., "An Exact Closed Form Solution for Fragmentation of Weibull Fibers in a Single Filament Composite with Applications to Fiber-Reinforced Ceramics", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 43, No. 10, 1995, pp. 1551-1585.
18. Baxevanakis, C., Jeulin, D. and Valentin, D., "Fracture Statistics of Single-Fiber Composite Specimens", *Comp. Sci. Tech.*, Vol. 48, 1993, pp. 47-56.
19. Feillard, P., Désarmot, G. and Favre, J.-P., "Theoretical Aspects of the Fragmentation Test", *Comp. Sci. Tech.*, Vol. 50, 1994, pp. 265-279.
20. Hild, F. and Feillard, P., "Ultimate Strength Properties of Fiber-Reinforced Composites", *Rel. Eng. Sys. Saf.*, Vol. 56, No. 3, 1997, pp. 225-235.
21. Press, W.H., Teukolsky, S.A., Vetterling, W.T. and Flannery, B.P., "*Numerical Recipes in Fortran*", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, MA (USA), 1992.